

without abdominal chalkiness, and cook flaky with good volume expansion.

In blast (Bl) screening trials at Ponnampet, the Bl hotspot in Karnataka, Sona Mahsuri was moderately resistant, with an average rating of 2.5 compared with 5.9 for Intan (Table 1).

In 26 trials since 1980, Sona Mahsuri has yielded an average 5.8 t/ha. In 12 trials, it yielded 6.0 t/ha compared to 5.4 t for Jaya (Table 2). In 1981-83 field trials at 14 sites in Mandya and Mysore, Sona Mahsuri yielded an average 6.5 t/ha compared with 5.4 t/ha for Mahsuri. At 6 other sites, it yielded an average 7.5 t/ha compared with 6.9 t for Prakash (Table 3).

Sona Mahsuri is gaining popularity and may soon be released for cultivation. ☞

Table 2. Sona Mahsuri grain yield in yield trials at Mandya, 1980-84.

Year	Yield (t/ha)	
	Sona Mahsuri	Saya
1980	5.8	5.2
1982	6.1	6.0
1983	6.3	5.4
1984	5.8	5.0
Av	6.0	5.4

Table 3. Sona Mahsuri grain yield in farm trials at Mysore and Mandya.

Year	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Sona Mahsuri	Check
		<i>Mahsuri</i>
1981	6.5	3.5
1982	7.0	6.5
1983	6.4	6.2
Av	6.6	5.4
		<i>Prakash</i>
1982	7.6	7.3
1984	7.5	6.6
Av	7.5	6.9

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IR13540-56-3-2-1: a promising rice for irrigated land in Bihar

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IR13540-56-3-2-1 (R. Heenati/ IR30 (BPHS)// IR2823-399-5) was chosen in 1981 kharif from the International Rice Yield Nursery - Medium. It matures in 130-135 d, is semidwarf, has good grain quality, and is suitable for irrigated, transplanted culture. IR13540-56-3-2-1 is moderately resistant to bacterial blight and will be a good substitute for Jaya and Sita, which have become susceptible.

In state trials from 1982 to 1984, IR13540-56-3-2-1 yielded consistently and 27% higher than Jaya and 20% more than Sita (Table 1, 2). It has been proposed for 1985 minikit trials in farmers' fields. ☞

Table 2. Mean yield of IR13540-56-3-2-1 and check varieties, 1982-84, Bihar, India.

Variety	Site					Mean
	Patna	Pusa	Sabour	Dhangain	Tilaundha	
	<i>Yield (t/ha)</i>					
IR13540-56-3-2-1	5.6	3.4	3.6	5.5	2.7	4.2
Jaya	3.7	3.1	2.6	4.4	2.6	3.3
Sita	3.8	2.9	3.0	4.9	2.7	3.5
	<i>Increase (%over Jaya)</i>					
IR 13540-56-3-2-1	51	10	38	23	4	27
	<i>Increase (%) over Sita</i>					
IR13540-56-3-2-1	47	17	20	12	0	20

Response of selected minikit rice varieties to nitrogen and tungro virus (RTV) on the Cauvery Delta

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Medium-duration IET7301, IET7303, IET7573, and IET7230 were compared with IR20 and Co 43 at TNRRI in Sep-Jan 1984. N was applied at 0, 40, 80, and 120 kg/ha. There was widespread RTV incidence and varieties were scored for infection.

Soil was a clay loam with low available N, medium P and K, and pH

Table 1. Performance of IR1 3540-56-3-2-1 in state variety trials in Bihar, India.

Trial location	Grain yield (t/ha)			CD at 5%
	IR13540-56-3-2-1	Jaya	Sita	
	<i>1982 kharif</i>			
Patna	5.4	3.4	3.6	1.0
Pusa	4.0	3.4	3.3	—
Sabour	3.6	2.1	3.1	0.5
Dhangain	6.3	5.1	5.6	0.8
Tilaundha	2.7	2.2	2.3	0.7
Mean	4.4	3.2	3.6	—
	<i>1983 kharif</i>			
Patna	7.3	4.2	4.0	1.3
Pusa	2.7	3.1	2.5	0.8
Sabour	3.6	2.7	3.0	0.5
Dhangain	4.8	4.4	4.9	0.9
Tilaundha	2.7	2.9	3.1	0.4
Mean	4.2	3.5	3.5	—
	<i>1984 kharif</i>			
Patna	4.2	3.6	3.7	0.9
Sabour	3.6	2.9	2.9	0.4
Dhangain	5.5	3.8	4.1	1.0
Mean	4.4	3.4	3.6	—

Table 1. Grain yield and RTV infection of varieties, Aduthurai, India.

Variety	RTV infection (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
IET7301	21-30	2.1 b
IET7303	6-10	3.8 a
IET7573	41-60	1.3 c
IET7230	41-60	0.6 c
Co 43	31-40	2.2 b
IR20	31-40	0.6 c

7.5. N was applied 50% basal and 25% at tillering and panicle initiation. P and K were applied basally at 50 kg/ha.

IET7303 had least RTV infection and yielded highest, followed by IET7301. IR20 had severe RTV infection and low